

FAILURE PROCESSES OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER OFF AXIS LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The failure behaviour of unidirectional composite plies under off axis loading is studied using standard off axis tests. The dependence of the stress distribution on the geometry of the specimens is analysed. Two different failure modes, this is, pure fiber breakage and pure inter fiber failure as well as a superposition of both are analysed based on test data and fracture patterns. The large difference in the ultimate load depending on the failure mode at small off axis angles is studied by varying the specimen length. The dependence of the stresses arising at potential fracture planes on the geometry and the off axis angle is investigated by finite element analyses.

1 INTRODUCTION

The plies in a laminate are loaded by multiaxial stresses. Because of their highly anisotropic mechanical properties the plies are very susceptible against loading transverse to the fibers. Even small off axis angles cause a significant reduction of stiffness and strength. In particular the failure process strongly depends on the off axis angle. Accordingly the strength under mixed mode loading is a key parameter for dimensioning laminates.

The off axis test is the anisotropic pendant to the standard uniaxial tensile test for isotropic materials. It is used to measure the mixed mode strength of anisotropic materials, in particular of unidirectional plies. Accordingly, off axis tests are utilised for the determination of the parameters of failure criteria. Furthermore the elastic constants including the shear modulus are measured. While in tensile tests of isotropic materials on one hand a sufficiently large zone of constant uniaxial stresses exists where the elastic constants can be measured and, on the other hand, isotropic materials predominantly fail under maximum tensile stresses none of these features is given for anisotropic materials. In case of inter fiber failure the potential fracture planes are defined by the fiber direction a priori. On these fracture planes a combination of normal and shear stresses is acting. Their ratio is controlled by the off axis angle.

Unidirectional plies of fiber reinforced composites are orthotropic materials as a matter of fact. However, orthotropic materials behave like fully anisotropic materials when loaded in axes other than the axes of orthotropy. The uncoupling of normal stresses from shear deformation and vice versa is lost. In a fully anisotropic material uniaxial tensile stresses give rise to a shear deformation (rhombic deformation). As a result, if the shear deformation is constrained shear stresses develop. To allow the shear deformation associated with an uniaxial stress state to develop a rotation of the specimen at the clamps is required. One possibility to enable the rotation is fixing the specimens by a form locking connection via a cylindrical bolt. However, this fixing suffers from friction problems. Since testing machines with rotating clamps are not available in general standard testing machines, equipped with non-rotating clamps, have to be used. In this case a non-homogeneous multiaxial stress state develops in the specimen. Additional stresses develop due to the constraining of the lateral contraction by the clamps which, however, is a common feature of all materials.

The prevention of the shear deformation (rhombic) taking place under uniaxial normal stresses in an anisotropic material causes a kind of bending of the specimen. Interestingly the amount of bending and even the direction strongly depends on the off axis angle. For the material under investigation the bending stresses increase with growing off axis angles. The maximum is reached at an off axis angle of about 30° . With further growing off axis angle the bending effect diminishes and vanishes completely at an angle of about 58° . For larger angles it changes its sign and reaches a small minimum before finally vanishing at 90° .

The phenomena of a constrained deformation of a fully anisotropic material were first visualised by Pagano and Halpin in the late sixties by performing experiments with steel reinforced rubber [1]. Chamis and Sinclair [2] performed experiments in order to measure the strength of composite plies under off axis loading. Later on several aspects of off axis testing were investigated, e.g. the influence of adhesion [3] as well as temperature [4] on the failure behaviour. Furthermore the determination of the shear modulus by off axis tests [5, 6] was analysed. Compressive [7] and dynamic loading [8] were studied as well as general aspects inherent in measuring the strength of composite plies [9, 10].

As a matter of fact the stress distribution in a specimen tested in a standard off axis test is far from ideal conditions required for the determination of the strength and the elastic properties. The question is if these discrepancies are tolerable and how they depend on the off axis angle. The aim of the present study is to analyse the amount of the deviation as well as its dependence on the off axis angle in combination with the length to width ratio for a representative composite material.

Two different failure modes appear in off axis tests depending on the specimen geometry and the off axis angle, this is, fiber breakage and inter fiber failure. If the geometry is such that a crack path parallel to the fibers can develop connecting the two free edges of the specimen without touching the clamped zones pure inter fiber failure occurs producing only one distinct crack. The influence of the failure mode on the ultimate load is studied by comparing two different specimen geometries. In case of very low angles fiber fracture occurs, accompanied by inter fiber failure.

2 MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

The material used for the present study is a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin with a fiber volume fraction of 55%. The specimens were cut out of plates consisting of five layers of unidirectional carbon fiber non crimped fabrics with a total thickness of 1.1 mm. The plates are of 50*50 mm in width and are manufactured in a vacuum assisted resin infusion device. The standard specimens have a width of 12 mm and a free length between the clamps of 70 mm. The clamped zones are covered with 1 mm thick tabs made of a quasi-isotropic glass fiber composite. The material data obtained from these tests are given in table 1.

Engineering constant	Value	
E_1	113.30	GPa
E_2	7.96	GPa
ν_{12}	0.32	-
G_{12}	4.00	GPa

Table 1: Engineering constants of CFRP specimen

The specimen type with a length to width ratio of 70/12 allows inter fiber failure to occur for off axis angles greater than 10° . For smaller angles any crack path starting at one edge has to run into the clamped ends of the specimen. Either the crack stops at the clamps and further cracks develop on parallel paths or fiber breakage occurs. The second specimen type has a length to width ratio of 280/12. This allows inter fiber failure to occur even for off axis angles down to 3° .

3 STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN OFF AXIS SPECIMENS

The finite element model presumes linear elastic orthotropic material. The analysis is restricted to plane stress conditions. Accordingly the three-dimensional stress state arising at the clamps is not taken into account at this stage. The clamps are not modelled explicitly but idealised by boundary conditions. The lateral displacement is prohibited while the axial displacements are prescribed to be constant over the cross section. One side is fixed, on the other side the loading is applied via prescribed displacements. The coordinate system is located in the center of the specimen. The x-axis is oriented in longitudinal direction of the specimen.

The axial stresses σ_{xx} vary significantly along the specimen length (x-coordinate) as well as over the cross section (y-coordinate). In Fig.1 the axial stresses are given for various cross sections along the specimen with the length to width ratio of 70/12 for a 15° off axis angle. The axial stresses in the middle cross section of the specimen (path10) increase from the edges to the center by more than 25%. With growing distance from the middle of the specimen the distribution of the stresses becomes more and more inhomogeneous, especially in the vicinity of the clamps. The maximum shifts towards the left edge (y=6 mm) and reaches two times the average stress close to the clamps (path 5). Since the system is antisymmetric the opposite behaviour is found on the other side of the specimen, respectively.

Figure 1: Longitudinal stresses in 15° off axis specimen at different cross sections along specimen axis

The disturbance of the stress field is depending on the specimen length to width ratio for a given off axis angle. If the specimen has a large length to width ratio, this is, the specimen is long and slender, the middle zone is far from the constraints caused by the clamps. This means that the shear deformation in the middle part can develop similar to a specimen tested with rotating clamps. As a result, almost pure uniaxial tensile stresses are present. In order to show the influence of the specimen geometry two lengths to width ratios are compared. In addition to the geometry used so far with a length to width ratio of 70/12, called short specimen in the following, a long specimen with a four times higher length to width ratio of 280/12 is used.

In Fig. 2a the axial stresses of the short specimen are plotted along the specimen length in the center line (path 2, y = 0 mm) as well as on the two edges of the specimen (path 1, path 3, y = +/-6 mm). The axial stresses of the short specimen along the center line are almost constant in the middle part and decrease towards the clamps (Fig. 2a). The stresses at the edges have a high maximum near the left or right clamp, respectively. After a steep decay they decrease almost linearly in the middle part and increases again towards the opposite clamp. In case of the long specimen the variation of the stresses is much lower even though sharp maxima occur at the clamps (Fig. 2b). Comparing the stress distributions of the two different lengths we have to keep in mind that the length scale of the graphs is different. The change of the stresses (first derivative) is four times as high in case of the short specimen.

Figure 2a: Longitudinal stresses in 15° off axis specimen, short specimen

Figure 2b: Longitudinal stresses in 15° off axis specimen, long specimen

Basic mechanics shows that in an uniaxial tensile test the shear stresses on potential fracture planes with small angles to the loading axis are dominating while with growing angle the stresses normal to the fracture plane become prevailing. This is basically true also for standard off axis tests even though the stress distribution is much more complicated compared with pure uniaxial tensile tests. For example the stress distribution along a potential fracture plane, this is parallel to the fibers, shows a significant deviation from that of an isotropic material. While in an isotropic material the stresses are constant along the plane they may strongly vary for anisotropic materials. For high off axis angles the situation is similar to isotropic materials, this is, the stresses normal to the fiber direction as well as the shear stresses parallel to it are almost constant along the plane. In Fig. 3a the stresses normal to the potential fracture planes are plotted for the short specimen. The values are normalised by the average normal stress. With growing off axis angle the stresses decrease in the middle of the potential fracture plane while increasing towards the edges. For an angle of 12° the stresses at the edges are five times that of the stresses in the middle. The results for off axis angles below 12° are not shown because the potential fracture planes necessarily touch at least one of the clamped ends of the specimens. The shear stresses behave in a very similar way even though the absolute variation is smaller.

Figure 3a: Normal stresses on potential failure plane, short specimen

Figure 3b: Normal stresses on potential failure plane, long specimen

The influence of the specimen length to width ratio on the stress distribution at potential fracture planes is very high for small off axis angles. In Fig. 3b the stresses normal to the potential fracture plane are shown for an off axis angle of 12° for the short as well as for the long specimen. In the long specimen the normal stresses in middle differ only by some percent from the stresses at the edges while in the short specimen the stresses at the edges are four times that of the middle. This shows that even if the specimen is long enough to fail under pure inter fiber failure the length to width ratio still has a massive influence stress distribution on the potential fracture planes and, accordingly, on the ultimate load.

4 EXPERIMENTAL

The off axis tests were performed for a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy system as described above. The off axis angles were varied between 0° and 90°. Since at small off axis angles the failure load strongly depends on the angle the off axis angles are varied in small steps of 3° between 0° and 15°. Between 15° and 30° steps of 5° were taken while the step size is 15° between 30° and 90°. The specimens were tested in a 100 kN standard testing machine equipped with hydraulic clamps. The loading speed was 0.5 mm/min. At least three to five tests were made for each off axis angle. For the determination of the elastic constants needed for the finite element analyses strain gauges in longitudinal and transverse direction were applied. The shear modulus was not measured separately but was calculated from the course of the longitudinal elastic modulus. The elastic constants measured are given in Table 1.

4.1 Off axis test for axial loading - off axis angle 0°

If the fibers are aligned in loading direction the failure occurs by instantaneous fiber fracture followed by additional inter fiber failure. The load/displacement curves do not show any significant damage, for example in form of load drops before the limit load is reached (Fig. 4). A large number of fiber breaks is found after final failure directly at the ends of the tabs where more or less high stress concentrations are present. In addition, due to local imperfections, several fiber breaks occur in the vicinity of the tabs. The high amount of energy stored in the specimens results in an extensive damage of the complete specimen in the moment of ultimate failure. During this highly dynamic process a large number of inter fiber cracks develops. The fracture surfaces forming in 0° off axis specimens are discussed in section 5.

Fig. 4: Load/displacement curves for short 0° off axis specimens – fiber breakage

4.2 Off axis test for 3° off axis angle

In case of a small off axis angle of 3° the failure stress is significantly lower compared to the axially loaded specimens and reaches only a little more than 50% of the respective 0° specimen (Fig. 9). This is due to the fact that the failure processes are completely different. While for the 0° specimen the failure is basically fiber breakage with only subsequent inter fiber failure the failure in case of a small off axis angle is initiated by inter fiber cracks which accumulate while the specimen is loaded. This is indicated by several load drops arising during the loading process (Fig. 5). The ultimate failure occurs by the breakage of the fibers. Even though the failure is not completely instantaneous noticeable by the load drops still a high amount of stored strain energy is suddenly released which also causes heavy damage. Extensive fiber breakage takes place while the crack path usually jumps several times along the specimen length causing massive additional inter fiber failure (Fig. 6). A large amount of fiber breaks occurs directly at the ends of the tabs, however, there is also considerable fiber breakage some millimeters away from the tabs.

Fig. 5: Load/displacement curves for short 3° off axis specimens – inter fiber failure plus fiber breakage

In addition to the longitudinal inter fiber cracks which are perpendicular to the upper and lower surfaces of the specimen and cut the whole thickness a second type of inter fiber failure occurs, this is, on planes parallel to the surfaces. This is assumed to be caused by the shock waves developing as a result of the high speed failure process. Since the fracture patterns of the specimen after total failure do not give sufficient information about the chronology of the failure process it is not possible to identify the initial and the subsequent phases of failure. To this end monitoring of the fracture process using a high speed camera is necessary. It is, however, complicated to identify thin fast running cracks in a black material.

Figure 6: Multiple fiber breaks and inter fiber cracks in a 3° off axis specimen

If the specimen length to width ratio is large enough to allow an inter fiber crack to run from one free edge to the other without striking the clamps the specimen will fail under pure inter fiber failure. In order to figure out how big the difference of the ultimate load is between pure inter fiber failure and fiber breakage a number of tests with long 3° specimen is performed. Indeed, a single inter fiber crack forms and only very little fiber breakage is found. The failure occurs instantaneously without any remarkably drop of the load, this is, without any previous failure (Fig. 7). The failure load is significantly lower compared to the short specimen (Fig. 5).

Fig. 7: Load/displacement curves for long 3° off axis specimens – inter fiber failure

4.3 Off axis test with pure inter fiber failure

For off axis angles larger than 10° pure inter fiber failure occurs without significant fiber fracture. A single crack forms running through the specimen. In figure 8 three specimens with an off axis angle of 45° are shown. The cracks start at different positions, only one beginning at the end of the tab where the highest stress concentrations exist. This behaviour is typical for all inter fiber cracks. Obviously local imperfections are responsible for the location of crack initiation. They exceed the stress concentrations induced by the clamping and the correspondent bending of the specimens.

Fig. 8: 45° off axis specimens – inter fiber failure at different locations

4.4 Strength versus off axis angle

The strong decrease of the strength at small off axis angles (Fig. 9) is caused by the weakness of unidirectional plies against stresses perpendicular to the fibers. In an ideal 0° specimen the fibers carry the almost the complete load and the interface is loaded only by secondary loads. The average maximum strength is about 1900 MPa. With the inclination of the fibers against the loading axis the interface is loaded directly by the external load even though the stresses are small due to the large fracture surface. In Fig. 9 the failure stresses of the 3° specimens for both failure modes – fiber fracture and pure inter fiber failure – are shown. The change of the failure mode results in a significant decrease of the strength by almost 30%. For all other angles the specimens have a length to width ratio allowing pure inter fiber failure. The strength decreases dramatically with growing off axis angle. For an angle of 30° the strength is only 5% of the strength of an axially loaded specimen. The strength perpendicular to the fibers (90° off axis angle) goes down to 2% of the maximal strength.

Figure 9: Strength vs off axis angle

The experimental findings show that results of different failure modes must not be mixed. The strength values should be separated into pure fiber breakage and pure inter fiber failure. Furthermore, pure fiber breakage should be restricted to pure axial loading as long as fiber fracture cannot be identified as the initial failure. The specimens for off axis tests should at least be long enough to allow pure inter fiber failure. In addition choosing the specimen geometry it should be kept in mind that the stress distribution on the fracture plane strongly depends on the length to width ratio for small off axis angles. As a result the length to width ratio should vary with the off axis angle. It should be chosen to yield to comparable stress distributions on the fracture planes. Otherwise the measured data are no actual material properties but they are geometry dependent parameters.

5 FRACTURE PATTERNS

The off axis experiments reveal some insight into the failure mechanisms in terms of assumptions made in common failure criteria. The so called mechanism based failure criteria proposed by Puck are based on the assumption that two failure modes can take place. The first failure type is pure fiber breakage. Fiber breakage is presumed to happen on planes perpendicular to the fibers cutting the whole cross section. This assumption is independent if the failure plane is under pure tensile or additional shear loading. The second failure type is pure inter fiber failure without fiber fracture.

In case of a 0° specimen where the loading is in fiber direction a very cliffy fracture surface forms (Fig. 10a). The specimen surface is visible on the upper and the left side of the micrograph. The micrograph is taken by a laser scanning microscope. Since the epoxy matrix is transparent the laser beam is also reflected by objects slightly below the surface. As a result some of the carbon fibers close to the surface of the specimen become visible. On the right hand side a combination of inter fiber failure and fiber fracture is visible. The fracture surface jumps over several layers of fibers in thickness direction. Accordingly fiber fracture does not necessarily occur separately but also in combination with inter fiber failure. This is not really surprising but the question is to which extent the assumptions the respective failure criteria are based on are reasonable. In addition, far from the major fracture zone also inter fiber cracks are found (Fig. 10b) indicating that the damage zone is not restricted to the main fracture zone but is very expanded.

Figure 10a: 0° specimen, inter fiber failure with simultaneous fiber fracture

Figure 10b: 0° specimen, inter fiber failure far from main fracture zone

CONCLUSIONS

Off axis tests performed with non-rotating clamps suffer from some inherent problems. Two principal different failure modes take place – fiber failure and inter fiber failure. Because these have nothing in common the measured data must be handled separately. Since the major mechanical property to be measured with off axis tests is the mixed mode strength transverse to the fibers the specimen length to width must be chosen to allow inter fiber failure for all angles except of pure axial

fiber loading, this is for 0°. The bending effect caused by the constrained deformation resulting in a non-homogeneous stress distribution on the potential fracture planes is highly depending on the off axis angle as well as on the length to width ratio of the specimen. As a result the length of the specimen should indeed be significantly longer than the minimum length necessary to allow pure inter fiber failure. It should be varied with the off axis angle in order to give comparable stress distributions on the fracture surfaces for all angles. For off axis angles greater than 30° and typical specimen geometries this effect is not crucial. However for small angles it becomes essential. This means that the specimen length to width ratio should be significantly increased for small off axis angles in order to get reliable strength data.

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